

A STUDY ON MATHEMATICAL ABILITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

P. Jeba Malar* & Dr. S. Praveen Kumar**

* M.Ed Scholar, N.V.K.S.D College of Education, Attoor, Kanniyakumari, Tamil Nadu

** Assistant Professor in Mathematics, N.V.K.S.D College of Education, Attoor, Kanniyakumari, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

The present study was intended to find out the mathematical ability of primary school students. The objective of the research study is to study the significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of primary school students with respect to gender, locale and type of management. The study used normative survey method. Mathematical Ability Test was used to conduct the study. The data were collected from 200 primary school students in various schools in Kanniyakumari district. For the analysis of data, the statistical technique used was t-test. The findings of the study reveal that there is a significance difference between in the mean scores of mathematical ability of primary school students with respect to gender, locality and type of management.

Key Words: Mathematical Ability, Primary School Students

Introduction:

The study of mathematics is crucial for schooling. Mathematics develops mathematical understanding in the form of basic abilities that students must possess to achieve other mathematical abilities to be able to understand mathematics material at a higher level. The capacity, proficiency, and aptitude of pupils in resolving simple mathematics issues constitute the fundamental mathematical ability. The goal of primary school education is to provide students with the necessary skills to function in society and to pursue higher education. As such, learning mathematics in school aims to develop students' ability to use mathematics not just in practical situations but also to reason mathematically in everyday situations. Mathematical ability is a human construct, which may be defined cognitively or pragmatically, depending on the purpose of definitions. Cognitive definitions are used when relating to this construct from a theoretical perspective; mathematical ability can then be defined as the ability to obtain, process, and retain mathematical information (Krutetskii 1976; Vilkomir and O'Donoghue 2009) or as the capacity to learn and master new mathematical ideas and skills (Koshy et al. 2009).

Need and Significance of the study

The foundation of human reasoning and intellect is mathematics, which is essential to any endeavour to comprehend the outside world or ourselves. It promotes logical reasoning and offers an efficient means of developing mental discipline. Knowing mathematics is essential to comprehending the material in other academic areas, including social science, science, and even sports, music, and the arts. Mathematical reasoning abilities, creativity, critical thinking, abstract or spatial thinking, problem solving ability, and even successful communication are some of the attributes that mathematics fosters. School children do not consider all the advantages that mathematics may offer them in the future; instead, they may view it as something dull, tough, and unimportant to their life. Students must choose an educational path that will prepare them for a lifetime of work as teachers, professors, mathematicians, engineers, statisticians, and scientists, even though all careers require a foundation in mathematics. Every student should have the chance to study important mathematics in detail and with comprehension so that they may demonstrate a variety of skills, aptitudes, and capacities. It is essential a study should be conducted to know about the mathematical proficiency of primary school pupils. Therefore, it is determined that a research on primary school students' mathematical ability is required.

Statement of the Problem:

In the present context, mathematical ability is very necessary for all students. Mathematical ability is more important in primary school students for their future. The present investigation is an attempt to study the mathematical ability of primary school students in different schools in Kanniyakumari district and is entitled as "A Study on Mathematical Ability of Primary School Students".

Objective of the Study:

The objective of the research study is to study the significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of primary school students with respect to gender, locality and type of management.

Hypotheses Framed:

- There is a significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of male and female primary school students.

- There is a significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of rural and urban female primary school students.
- There is a significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of aided and private primary school students.

Methodology in Brief:

- Method used: Normative survey method was used for the study.
- Sample: The sample for the study comprised of 200 primary school students.
- Tool Used: The tool used for the study is Mathematical Ability Test developed by Kumar S P (2011).
- Statistical Technique Used: In the present study the following statistical techniques used was t-test.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1: Comparison of mathematical ability among primary school student based on gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P	Remark
Ability Test	Male	96	18.43	5.376	-2.968	0.03	S

From the table 1, it is clear that $P < 0.05$ and it is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, there exists significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of boys and girls.

Table 2: Comparison of mathematical ability among primary school student based on locale

	Locale	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P	Remark
Ability Test	Rural	87	21.44	3.967	5.134	0.00	S

From the table 2, it is clear that $P < 0.05$ and it is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, there exists significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of rural and urban.

Table 3: Comparison of mathematical ability among primary school student based on type of school

	Type of Management	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P	Remark
Ability Test	Aided	67	20.84	3.968	2.745	0.007	NS

From the table 3, it is clear that $P > 0.05$ and it is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, there exists no significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of aided and private schools.

Findings of the Study:

- There exists significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of boys and girls.
- There exists significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of rural and urban.
- There exists no significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of aided and private schools.

Suggestion for Further Study:

- The present research study can be conducted on Government and ICSE primary school students.
- This study can be conducted on primary school students all over the Tamil Nadu state.

Conclusion:

The mathematical ability is most important to all students because mathematics develop creativity, critical thinking, abstract or spatial thinking, problem solving ability, and even successful communication. The study reveals that there exists significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of primary school students with respect to gender and locality and there exists no significance difference in the mean scores of mathematical ability of type of management in primary school students. It is the need for mathematics teachers to develop the mathematical ability of students.

References:

1. Koshy V, Ernest P, Casey R. (2009). Mathematically Gifted and Talented Learners: Theory and Practice. Int J Math Edu Sci Technology, 40(2):213-228
2. Krutetskii, V A (1976). The Psychology of Mathematical Abilities in School Children. University of Chicago Press, Chicago
3. Raja, D.W.B., Kumar, P.S., (2011). Special Education: Focus on Mathematics Learning Disability. APH Publishing Corporation.
4. Vijayalakshmi, S, R, Kumar, Sharath, S.R., (2023) Attitude towards Mathematics among Secondary School Students. Eduttract, 23(3).
5. Zainal, Zaid. (2019), Analysis of Students' Basic Mathematical Ability In Primary Schoolteacher Education Study Program State University Of Makassar ICSTEE, , Makassar, Indonesia EAI DOI 10.4108/eai.14-9-2019.2290037